

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18470728>

IMPROVING FIRE RESISTANCE OF TUBULAR STEEL STRUCTURES

Kh.A. Kurbanov,

Candidate of Technical Sciences, Professor

(Academy of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Uzbekistan)

Email: kholmurod.kurbanov@gmail.com

Abstract. *The limited fire resistance of steel structures without further enhancement constrains their widespread use in construction. The most effective method for increasing their fire resistance is water cooling. In this case, water can be supplied to both the surface and the interior of the structure. Pipelines of rod-type lightweight structures, such as the "Kislovodsk" module, simultaneously perform the functions of load-bearing structure, automatic fire suppression (as part of sprinkler system), and self-regulating cooling. The article presents the results of research and recommendations for improving the fire resistance of steel structures.*

Keywords: *Metal, structure, fire resistance, fire extinguishing, cooling, temperature, hydraulic resistance, Reynolds number.*

Annotatsiya. *Metal konstruktsiyalarning past yong'inbardoshlik darajasiga ega ekanligi ularni qurilishda keng qo'llanilishini chegaralab qo'yadi. Ularning yong'inbardoshligini oshirish usullaridan eng samaralisi suv bilan sovutish hisoblanadi. Bunda suv sirt tomoniga ham ichiga ham berilishi mumkin. «Kislovodsk» moduli kabi sterjenli yengil konstruktsiyalarning quvurlari bir vaqtning o'zida ham yuk ko'tarish vazifasini, ham avtomatik yong'in o'chirish uskunaasi va o'z-o'zini sovutish vazifalarini bajaradi. Metal konstruktsiyalarning yong'inbardoshligini oshirish bo'yicha o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlar natijasi va tavsiyalar keltirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Metal, konstruktsiya, yong'inbardoshlik, yong'in o'chirish, sovutish, harorat, gidravlik qarshilik, Reynold's soni.*

***Аннотация.** Низкая степень огнестойкости металлических конструкций ограничивает их широкое применение в строительстве. Наиболее эффективным методом повышения их огнестойкости является водяное охлаждение. При этом вода может подаваться как на поверхность, так и внутрь конструкции. Трубопроводы стержневых лёгких конструкций, подобные модулю «Кисловодск», одновременно выполняют функции несущей конструкции, автоматического пожаротушения и саморегулирующегося охлаждения. В статье представлены результаты исследований и рекомендации по повышению огнестойкости металлических конструкций.*

***Ключевые слова:** Металл, конструкция, огнестойкость, пожаротушение, охлаждение, температура, гидравлическое сопротивление, число Рейнольдса.*

Lightweight tubular unprotected steel structures, such as the "Kislovodsk" module, are commonly used for spanning large areas. However, they have very limited fire resistance. The need for fire protection of steel structures stems from the high sensitivity of steel to elevated temperatures and fire exposure. Due to their high thermal conductivity, these structures heat up rapidly and lose their mechanical properties, which limits the application of unprotected steel structures. The actual fire resistance limit of steel structures varies from 0.1 to 0.4 hours, depending on element thickness and magnitude of applied stresses. Practical methods currently employed to improve fire resistance such as coating with plaster, fire-resistant paints, concrete encasement and similar measures are highly labour-intensive, significantly increase structural weight, and deteriorate over time due to dynamic (seismic) impacts and changes in adhesive properties resulting from temperature fluctuations.

In our view, the most effective method for improving the fire resistance of steel structures is filling them with water combined with automatic self-spraying [1]. In this case, the tubular elements of the structures simultaneously serve as load-bearing members, components of an automatic fire suppression system, and self-cooling mechanisms for the structure.

The basic concept of fire protection through water cooling is not a recent innovation. As early as 1884, American J. Wright patented the use of cast iron columns with water cooling to protect buildings from fire. In France, a similar patent was issued to P. Mülten only in 1960.

Consequently, provided that water circulation within the structure proceeds correctly, unlimited fire resistance can be achieved [2]. Furthermore, such a system can serve as a means for creating artificial climate control in buildings, as was the case in

the development of an air conditioning system for an office building and swimming pool in the Federal Republic of Germany.

Based on analysis of literature data, the following objective was formulated: to investigate the temperature regime of lightweight steel structures and develop recommendations for improving their fire resistance.

It is known that as the water flow velocity in the pipe increases, the pipe wall temperature decreases. Furthermore, the pipe wall temperature ($T_{pipe\ wall}$) depends on the room mean volumetric temperature (T_{room}), pipe diameter (d), fluid viscosity, and other factors that is, there exists the following functional relationship between them:

$$T_{pipe\ wall} = f(T_{room}, V, d, \nu) \quad (1)$$

Applying the theory of dimensions to the functional relationship (1), it can be represented in the following form:

$$\frac{T_{pipe\ wall}}{T_{room}} = f(Re) \quad (2)$$

From which it is evident that the pipe wall temperature depends on the mean volume temperature and the Reynolds number.

In order to study the influence of these factors on the fire resistance of tubular steel structures, we conducted experimental investigations of the temperature regime of a structural element. A single pipe with a diameter of $d=60$ mm and length $l=4$ m was selected as the structural element. The experiments were conducted in a furnace where, using four gas burners, the mean volume temperature was brought to 900–1000°C. In each test, the temperature rise dynamics of the mean volume temperature were identical to the standard fire temperature curve.

To investigate the temperature regime of the structure and hydraulic parameters of flow in the pipes, a full-scale fragment of the "Kislovodsk" module with dimensions of $6 \times 6 \times 2.12$ m was constructed. The total number of rods used in the fragment is 32 units. They are divided into 7 independent lines connected to a main supply pipe (Fig. 1).

Characteristic shunts were selected for investigation, which differ in connection angles, diameters of connected rods, and other parameters (Fig. 1).

Pressure drops across the connection nodes was measured using a mercury differential manometer DT-50, which was connected via a fitting to the rods upstream and downstream of the shunts. The distance from the fitting to the shunt and from the shunt to the downstream fitting was selected to ensure the formation of a smoothly varying or parallel-jet flow. Pressure upstream of the discharge opening and at characteristic points was measured using a pressure gauge MTP-600.

Fig. 1. Fragment of a steel tubular structure.

(1 – pipes with diameter 60 mm; 2 – pipes with diameter 76 mm)

The water flow velocity was determined as the ratio of water flow rate to the pipe cross-sectional area. Water flow rate was measured volumetrically. A rectangular tank with a volume of 100 litres was used as the measuring vessel.

Analysis of the obtained data showed a tendency for the resistance coefficient of the connection node to decrease with increasing flow velocity. In the range of flow

velocity variation in the shunt (pipe junction, PJ) from 2 m/s to 4 m/s, the values of the total resistance coefficient decreased by 9% to 20%.

It is known that under steady-state flow conditions, the local resistance coefficient ξ generally depends on the Reynolds number (Re) and Θ (a parameter characterising the ratio of resistance dimensions) [2].

Analysis of the graph showing the dependence of the total resistance coefficient of the connection node on the Reynolds number (Fig. 2), constructed from measurement data at characteristic nodes, demonstrated that the experimental data are adequately approximated by an equation of the form:

$$\xi = \kappa \cdot e^{a \cdot Re}, \quad (3)$$

where a is a coefficient that is constant for all characteristic nodes: $a = -5.46 \times 10^{-6}$; k is a coefficient that depends on the type of connection. For example: for node *No. 1*, $k = 3.53$; for node *No. 2*, $k = 3.44$; for node *No. 4*, $k = 3.14$; for node *No. 5*, $k = 3.68$.

Comparison of the obtained data with theoretical values showed that the experimental values of the total resistance coefficient slightly exceed the theoretical ones. This is apparently explained by the surface finish irregularities of the connection nodes and the range of Reynolds number variation. However, it should be noted that the theoretical formulas apply to the quadratic resistance region, where the resistance coefficient ξ is independent of Re .

During investigation of the structure's temperature regime, the room mean volume temperature and pipe wall temperature were simultaneously recorded at three points and then averaged. Thermocouples for measuring wall temperature were installed slightly recessed into the wall and secured with metal clamps. Water temperature at the inlet and outlet of the pipe section was measured using thermocouples inserted into the axial part of the flow. Additionally, water temperature at the pipe inlet and outlet was verified using a standard thermometer. Chromel-Alumel (XA) thermocouples were used for temperature measurement, with KSP-4 secondary instruments and millivoltmeters XA-68 and MV-52, which have a measurement accuracy of $\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$.

Based on the obtained results, graphs were constructed showing the dynamics of mean volume temperature, pipe wall temperature, and water outlet temperature at various mean water flow velocities (minimum mean velocity $V = 7$ cm/s).

Fig. 2. Graphs showing the variation of mean volume temperature and pipe wall temperature as a function of Reynolds number.

Analysis of these graphs showed that as water flow velocity in the pipe increases the rate of change of pipe wall temperature decreases. The character of pipe wall temperature decrease as a function of water flow velocity demonstrates that the shape of the curves for various fixed mean volume temperature values remains constant that is, it does not change.

Results of data processing according to functional relationship (2) showed that the relationship between relative temperature and Reynolds number is adequately approximated by the following dependence:

$$\frac{T_{pipe\ wall}}{T_{room}} = k \cdot (Re)^{-0,55} \quad (4)$$

The value of coefficient K within the range of available data varies within the following limits:

$$\text{at } T_{room} = 720^{\circ}C, \quad K = 29.4 \quad \text{at } T_{room} = 820^{\circ}C, \quad K = 38.1$$

$$\text{at } T_{room} = 770^{\circ}C, \quad K = 33.6 \quad \text{at } T_{room} = 930^{\circ}C, \quad K = 49.04$$

Analysis of these data showed that as a first approximation, the value of K can be determined by the formula:

$$k = 5,67 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot T_{room}^2 \quad (5)$$

Then, for practical calculations to determine pipe wall temperature, the following equation can be used:

$$T_{pipe\ wall} = \frac{5,67 \cdot 10^{-5}}{(Re)^{0,55}} \cdot T_{room}^3 \quad (6)$$

Thus, based on the conducted investigations, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. For hydraulic calculations of similar structures, the values of the total resistance coefficient of connection nodes are recommended to be determined using formula (3).
2. The most effective method for improving fire resistance of tubular steel structures is water cooling by supplying water directly inside the tubular structures while ensuring water circulation.
3. During water circulation, the pipe wall temperature is significantly reduced depending on the water flow velocity in the pipes. For practical calculations to determine pipe wall temperature during fire, equation (4) can be used, with coefficient K values recommended to be determined using formula (5).

References

1. Худоев А.Д., Буриев Т., Абдуллаев Э.Р. Повышение взрывопожарной безопасности покрытий зданий категорированных объектов, эксплуатирующихся в условиях сейсмических воздействий. II. Пожаровзрывобезопасность, Москва. Т11. №1 2002 г. с.45-51
2. Курбанов Х.А. Повышение огнестойкости многостержневых трубчатых металлических конструкций. Пожаровзрывобезопасность, Ташкент. №1 2018 г. с.113-116
3. Курбанов Х.А., Абобакиров И. Енгил метал конструкцияларнинг ёнғинбардошлик даражасини ошириш. Журнал “Ёнғин хавфсизлиги”, Ташкент. 2012 й., №4. б.78-81
4. Киселев П.Г. Гидравлика, основы механики жидкости.-М.:Энергия,1980г.
5. Идельчик И.Е. Справочник по гидравлическим сопротивлениям.-М.,1975г.